

1 **Nuclear transport pathways are activated by HPV16 E5.**

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6 We previously discovered a nuclear retention signal (NES) in the high risk HPV16 L2 protein which
7 mediated retention of the high risk minor capsid protein in the nucleus. Nuclear transport of cellular
8 cargoes is commonly exploited by viruses during infection. We demonstrate here activation of nuclear
9 transport by the early E5 protein of HPV type 16. We report specific activation of import receptors
10 Karyopherin *KPNA6* and Importin *IPO13*.

11 Citations

12 1. Mamoor, S., Onder, Z., Karanam, B., Kwak, K., Bordeaux, J., Crosby, L., Roden, R.B. and
13 Moroianu, J., 2012. The high risk HPV16 L2 minor capsid protein has multiple transport signals that
14 mediate its nucleocytoplasmic traffic. *Virology*, 422(2), pp.413-424.